

nucleophilic attack by the amide group of the penultimate unit in the polymer^{6,7}. Such nucleophilic displacement is facilitated in water⁸. This effect is pronounced with Br than with Cl end group^{6,7}. Also, this and other undesirable side reactions such as the thermal initiation become increasingly important with the increase in temperature. It is therefore desirable to carry out the ATRP in an aqueous based medium at low temperature.

Masci *et al.* successfully carried out ATRP of *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAM) and *N,N*-dimethylacrylamide (DMA) as well as anionically charged acrylamide derivatives in aqueous DMF medium using CuCl/tris(2-dimethylaminoethyl)-amine (Me₆TREN) as the catalyst⁹⁻¹¹. This catalyst complex was used earlier by Teodorescu and Matyjaszewski in the ATRP of DMA and some other substituted acrylamides in toluene or DMF at room temperature¹². The polymerization in this latter case gave limited yield and molecular weight, $M_n \sim 10000$ which was attributed to catalyst poisoning. However, narrow distribution polymers were obtained. In a subsequent work Naugebauer and Matyjaszewski improved upon the molecular weight and yield by adjusting the initial reaction conditions¹³. Subsequently, Xiao and Wirth used this catalyst complex along with added deactivator CuCl₂ (10 mol% of CuCl) for the surface bound benzyl chloride initiated polymerization of acrylamide on silica in DMF at room temperature¹⁴. However, kinetic analysis revealed predominant termination. Microanalysis results indicated loss of chlorine end group. Gopireddy and Husson also

reported nonliving polymerization of acrylamide grown from surface-bound initiators using this same catalyst¹⁵. However, termination is difficult to prevent in a surface-initiated polymerization because the radicals are generated in close proximity¹⁴. In this work we have therefore studied the solution ATRP of acrylamide in DMF-water medium using the CuCl/Me₆TREN catalyst complex.

Since the earlier work in this laboratory^{2,3,16} revealed that CuCl works better than CuBr in the ATRP of acrylamide we have used CuCl/Me₆TREN complex as the catalyst and 2-chloropropanamide as the initiator. Also, CuCl₂/Me₆TREN and LiCl have been used as the additives in order to compensate/prevent the activator loss through aquation. LiCl also helped to keep the polymer in solution at low temperature *ca.* 0 °C.

Results and discussion

In previous works from our laboratory Bpy and PMDETA were used as ligands for CuCl catalyst in the ATRP of acrylamide. In this work Me₆TREN has been used as the ligand which gives a more active Cu^I catalyst complex¹⁷. Also, as mentioned in the introduction, it reportedly worked well in the ATRP of NIPAM and DMA in DMF/water medium at 20 °C⁹.

We first studied the polymerization at room temperature (30 °C) in DMF/water medium (50–70 vol. % DMF) of various compositions. The results are shown in Table 1. This range of solvent composition was chosen in order to optimise two aspects, i.e. complete solubility of the

Table 1. Results of ATRP of acrylamide in various DMF-H₂O mixtures at 30 °C
[Acrylamide] = 4.22 mol/dm³, [2-Cl-PA] = 0.02 mol/dm³,
[CuCl] = 0.02 mol/dm³ and [Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [Me₆TREN] = 1 : 1, time = 18 h

Entry	Solvent %DMF (v/v)	In presence of		% Conversion	M _n (Theory)	M _n (GPC)	PDI
		LiCl (M)	CuCl ₂ : CuCl				
1	50	0	0	22	3300	1490	1.36
2	60	0	0	11	1650	810	1.39
3	70	0	0	18	2700	1720	1.36
4	50	0	0.2	31	4650	4310	1.39
5	60	0	0.2	23	3450	5830	1.33
6	70	0	0.2	16	2400	4160	1.40
7	50	1	0.2	49	7350	2130	1.39
8	60	1	0.2	41	6150	1720	1.32
9	70	1	0.2	35	5250	1450	1.29
10	70	2	0.2	40	6000	2760	1.52
11	70	0.5	0.2	20	3000	2000	1.26
12	70	0.2	0.2	18	2700	3320	1.25

ingredients including the polymer produced and minimise aequation of the complex as well as hydrolysis of the dormant alkyl halide species. Without using any additive (CuCl_2 and/or LiCl) the yield was very low and the PDI was ~ 1.4 (entries 1–3). The theoretical and experimental molecular weights also did not match well. Further, the addition of CuCl_2 gave no significant improvement. Only the yield improved with the use of 50 and 60 vol. % of DMF (entries 4–6). With the addition of the water soluble halide salt, LiCl , the yield improved. The amount of LiCl added to the system was then varied. On increasing the quantity of LiCl from 1 *M* to 2 *M*, the yield improved, but at the cost of PDI which worsened from 1.29 to 1.52 (vide entries 9 and 10 of Table 1). Similarly, decreasing the quantity of LiCl from 1 *M* decreased the yield considerably (vide entries 11 and 12 of Table 1). The results thus show that the addition of CuCl_2 and LiCl does not help in lowering the PDI. This means that the radical deactivation by the cupric complex is not an important reaction.

The effect of varying the temperature of polymerization from 30 to 130 °C was also studied. The results are shown in Table 2. Increasing the temperature from 30 to 60 °C resulted in a poorer yield and higher PDI of the polymer (entries 1 and 2). Further increase of temperature to 130 °C worsened the results (entry 3). Lowering the temperature to 0 °C gave the highest yield (entry 4). Further lowering the temperature to –20 °C gave a diminished return (entry 5). However, the last inference was not conclusive as the DMF content was different. In the latter case the experiment was done in 60% DMF medium with the expectation of achieving complete solubility of the polymer produced at –20 °C. At 0 °C precipitation also occurs if LiCl is not added.

It is evident from the results given in Table 3 that using the additives i.e. LiCl and CuCl the PDI improves

Table 2. Results of ATRP of acrylamide carried out at different temperatures in various DMF- H_2O mixtures
[Acrylamide] = 4.22 mol/dm³, [LiCl] = 1 *M*,
[2-Cl-PA] = [CuCl] = 0.02 mol/dm³,
[CuCl₂]/[CuCl] = 0.2 and
[Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [Me₆TREN] = 1 : 1, time = 18 h

Entry	Temp. (°C)	Solvent %DMF (v/v)	% Conversion	M _n (Theory)	M _n (GPC)	PDI
1	30	70	35	5250	1450	1.29
2	60	70	13	1950	2300	1.43
3	130	70	11	1650	1950	1.51
4	0	70	49	7350	5350	1.29
5	–20	60	28 ^a	4200	3560	1.24

^aPolymer precipitates.

only marginally. This may be due to the prevention of the precipitation of the polymer when LiCl is used. The effect of the cation of the added chloride was also investigated. The results given in Table 4 show that replacement of LiCl with KCl or NH_4Cl does not effect any improvement on the PDI, but the yield decreases.

In order to lower the PDI two approaches were made. In one the initiator concentration was reduced from 0.02 mol/dm³ to 0.01 mol/dm³ and the concentration of the added deactivator $\text{CuCl}_2/\text{Me}_6\text{TREN}$ was increased in order to reduce the radical concentration. The CuCl_2 concentration was kept equal to that of CuCl . The result is shown in Table 5 (entry 1). This approach resulted in a lower PDI viz. 1.12. On further increasing the concentration of CuCl_2 to twice that of CuCl no further improvement occurred. Rather the PDI increased somewhat (entry 2). In the other approach the concentration of the catalyst was reduced in order to reduce the radical concentration (entry 3, Table 5). The polymer obtained had low PDI. On decreasing the amount of the catalyst fur-

Table 3. Results of ATRP of acrylamide in various DMF- H_2O mixtures at 0 °C
[Acrylamide] = 4.22 mol/dm³, [2-Cl-PA] = 0.02 mol/dm³, [CuCl] = 0.02 mol/dm³ and
[Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [Me₆TREN] = 1 : 1, time = 18 h

Entry	Solvent %DMF (v/v)	In presence of		% Conversion	M _n (Theory)	M _n (GPC)	PDI
		LiCl (<i>M</i>)	CuCl_2 : CuCl				
1	50	0	0	75 ^a	11250	11700	1.35
2	60	0	0	65 ^a	9750	8150	1.36
3	70	0	0	66 ^a	9900	7700	1.33
4	60	1	0.2	76	11400	9720	1.32
5	70	1	0.2	49	7350	5350	1.29

^aPolymer precipitates.

Table 4. Results of ATRP of acrylamide in 70% DMF (v/v)-H₂O at 0 °C using different water soluble halide salts in 1 M concentration
 [Acrylamide] = 4.22 mol/dm³, [2-Cl-PA] = 0.02 mol/dm³, [CuCl] = 0.02 mol/dm³, [CuCh]/[CuCl] = 0.2 and [Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [Me₆TREN] = 1 : 1, time = 18 h

Entry	Halide salt	% Conversion	M _n (Theory)	M _n (GPC)	PDI
1	LiCl	49	7350	5350	1.29
2	KCl	16	2400	2320	1.25
3	NH ₄ Cl	26	3900	3080	1.3

ther from 0.004 mol/dm³ to 0.002 mol/dm³ the yield decreased sharply (entry 4, Table 5). This result implies that the reaction is not facile with such a small catalyst concentration relative to the initiator concentration and also that the limited conversion depends on the catalyst/initiator ratio. Higher is the ratio, higher is the conversion which is in accordance with that of Teodorescu *et al.*¹².

Kinetic studies of two selected systems (entries 2 and 3 of Table 5) were also done. The first order kinetic plots for monomer disappearance are not linear (Fig. 1). From the figure it is evident that the slopes of both the curves are steeper in the beginning which flatten latter. This implies that the rates of polymerization are high in the beginning which decrease continuously as the polymerization progress. Moreover the conversions were not complete. These results indicate the presence of termination reactions or catalyst deactivation, as was reported for the DMA polymerization in toluene¹².

Fig. 1. First order kinetic plot of ATRP of acrylamide in 60 vol. % DMF : H₂O at 0 °C. [Acrylamide] = 4.22 mol/dm³, [Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [Me₆TREN] = 1 : 1, [LiCl] = 1 mol/dm³, (●) [2-Cl-PA] = [Cu^I] = [Cu^{II}] = 0.01 mol/dm³ (■) [2-Cl-PA] = 0.02 mol/dm³, [Cu^I] = [Cu^{II}] = 0.004 mol/dm³.

In order to test the livingness of the polymers the chain extension experiments were carried out using a polyacrylamide sample of narrow PDI = (1.15, entry 3 of Table 5). But repeated attempts (both one and two pot methods) failed to produce chain extension. Thus, the polymers formed were dead. A chain extension experiment was even carried out using as macroinitiator the polymer of entry 3 in Table 5, isolated at lower conversion (38%). This attempt also did not succeed. The chain extension experiment results indicate that the halide end group was lost. In order to test if the halide end group is

Fig. 2. NMR spectra of (i) : 2-Cl-PA, (ii) : PAM prepared in 60 vol. % DMF medium at 0 °C (both the samples are dissolved in D₂O).

present or not following polymerization, the ^1H nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra of the initiator and of the polymer were taken. Both the spectra are shown in Fig. 2. From the spectrum 2(i) of the initiator 2-chloropropanamide it may be seen that the methine proton (b) appears at a much lower field ($\delta = 4.39$ ppm) due to the carbon being attached to electron withdrawing Cl atom and CONH_2 group. The absence of any signal in this region in the polymer spectrum 2(ii) indicates the absence of Cl end group in the polymer. The broad signals at $\delta = 1.55$ of proton (c) and $\delta = 2.09$ of proton (d) of the polymer in Fig. 2(ii) indicates that the resonances are not resolved. This happens in polyacrylamide due to its highly associating nature. We also obtained the spectrum at a higher temperature *ca.* 90 °C, but the fine structures did not appear (not shown). For this reason it has not been possible to identify the resonance ($\delta = 3.25$) in Fig. 2(ii).

The absence of Cl end group is difficult to reconcile with the increase of molecular weights with increase in conversion, as is evident from Fig. 3 where a plot of molecular weight vs conversion is given. This plot shows that the molecular weight is much lower than the theoretical value at lower conversions but it increases rapidly with increase in conversion and approaches the theoretical value at higher conversions, *ca.* 45%. The GPC traces, as shown in Fig. 4, progressively shift to higher molecular weights region with the increase in conversion. However, it has been reported in the literature that molecular weights increase with conversion, even if termination of polymer radicals occur, provided initiation is very fast and complete and also radical transfer reaction does not occur¹⁸. The present polymerization system seems to belong to this latter category and nonliving.

Experimental

Materials :

Acrylamide (>99% electrophoresis grade; Sigma), 2-chloropropanamide (2-Cl-PA; 98%) and dimethylformamide

Fig. 3. Plots of molecular weight and PDI vs % conversion of polyacrylamide prepared in 60 vol. % DMF medium at 0 °C. Polymerization recipe : [acrylamide] = 4.22 mol/dm³, [LiCl] = 1 mol/dm³, [2-Cl-PA] = [Cu^I] = [Cu^{II}] = 0.01 mol/dm³ and [Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [Me₆TREN] = 1 : 1.

(DMF) (Merck GR grade) were used as received. CuCl was purified by washing with the corresponding acids (10% HCl in water) followed by methanol and diethyl ether in a Schlenk tube under a nitrogen atmosphere^{2,3}. Commercial distilled water was redistilled over alkaline permanganate.

Polymerization :

Water and DMF were purged with nitrogen in two separate vessels and sealed with rubber septums. In a N₂ purged 8 cm × 2.5 cm test tube provided with a B-19 standard joint acrylamide (900 mg, 12.67 mmol) and LiCl (132 mg, 3.18 mmol) were introduced followed by 1.8 ml DMF and 1.2 ml water. CuCl₂ (2.05 mg, 0.012 mmol), CuCl (1.18 mg, 0.012 mmol) and 2-Cl-PA (6.5 mg, 0.06 mmol) were next added into the tube sequentially in that order while purging with nitrogen was continued for 30 min. The reaction vessel was then sealed with a rubber septum, which was secured by Cu wire. It was then placed in a constant temperature bath. After thermal equilibrium was reached, Me₆TREN (6.6 μl, 0.024 mmol) was added

Table 5. Results of ATRP of acrylamide in 60 vol. % DMF-H₂O at 0 °C [Acrylamide] = 4.22 mol/dm³, [Cu^I + Cu^{II}] : [Me₆TREN] = 1 : 1 and [LiCl] = 1 mol/dm³, time = 18 h

Entry	[2-Cl-PA] mol/dm ³	[2-Cl-PA] : Cu ^I : Cu ^{II}	% Conversion	M_n (Theory)	M_n (GPC)	PDI
1	0.01	1 : 1 : 1	45	12900	11900	1.12
2	0.01	1 : 1 : 2	47	14100	12000	1.17
3	0.02	1 : 0.2 : 0.2	57	8550	6930	1.15
4	0.02	1 : 0.1 : 0.2	21	3150	2930	1.28

Fig. 4. Shift of GPC traces of polymers taken out at different time intervals, to higher molecular weight region observed in the kinetic study of ATRP of acrylamide in 60 vol. % DMF medium at 0 °C. Recipe is same that of Fig. 3.

into the tube using a gas-tight Hamilton microsyringe. After 18 h the reaction vessel was taken out of the bath and the polymer was precipitated into methanol. The precipitated polymer was a white powder which was separated by centrifugation, redispersed in methanol and then recovered after centrifugation. This cycle was repeated twice. The obtained polymer was dried in a vacuum oven at 45 °C for 48 h. The samples for kinetic studies were withdrawn at suitable time intervals with gas-tight syringes and the polymers were isolated, purified and dried as above.

Chain extension :

An example is given below.

The polymers obtained in experiments described in the previous paragraph were used as macro initiators for chain extension experiments. In a two pot procedure PAM was prepared as described above. Polyacrylamide (300 mg) was taken in a reaction vessel previously purged with N₂. Water (1 ml) previously purged with N₂ was added into the tube and the system was kept for 24 h for complete dissolution of the polymer. Then to the solution DMF (1.5 ml) (also previously purged with N₂) was added dropwise while simultaneously purging with nitrogen was continued. Acrylamide (450 mg, 6.33 mmol), LiCl (110 mg, 2.65 mmol), CuCl₂ (2.55 mg, 0.015 mmol), CuCl (1.48 mg, 0.015 mmol) were next added into the tube in that order while purging with nitrogen was on. The vessel was then sealed with a rubber septum which was se-

cured by a copper wire and put into a constant temperature bath at 0 °C. Then after thermal equilibrium was reached, Me₆TREN (8.3 μl, 0.03 mmol) was added into the tube using a gas-tight Hamilton microsyringe. The reaction was continued for 24 h. The polymer obtained was precipitated and purified as described above.

The two-pot experiment was also conducted under high vacuum. The procedure was as follows. An H-tube, with limbs bulged at the bottom and fitted with two A10 Standard joints was used as the reaction vessel. It was purged with nitrogen for 2 min and then into the bulb of the right limb PAM (300 mg) and 0.6 ml of nitrogen purged water were added while nitrogen flow was maintained through the other limb. Both the limbs were sealed with rubber septum and the polymer was dissolved overnight. Then in the bulb of the other limb were introduced the other ingredients; acrylamide, LiCl, CuCl₂, CuCl and Me₆TREN (quantities as mentioned in the previous paragraph), 0.4 ml water and 1.5 ml DMF (both previously purged with nitrogen) while nitrogen was blown. This limb was then closed with the stopper of the standard joint. The contents in both the limbs were then frozen by dipping the bulbs in liquid nitrogen. Then the system was connected to a high vacuum line (2 × 10⁻⁵ mm Hg) by quickly opening the rubber septum of the first limb and connecting it to the high vacuum line. The solutions were freed from oxygen by evacuation. The evacuation was repeated between three freeze-thaw cycles. Then the two limbs of the H-tube were sealed using a sealing torch. After thawing the contents of the bulbs in the limbs, the solution in the left limb was mixed with that in the right limb by tilting the H-tube. The mixture was then kept in a constant temperature bath at 0 °C. After 24 h the sealed limbs were opened and the polymer was precipitated and purified as described above.

One-pot procedures were also followed under either N₂ atmosphere or high vacuum.

Characterization :

The molecular weights and their distribution (MWD) were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) at room temperature (*ca.* 30 °C) with a Waters 510 HPLC pump, a Waters series 400 differential refractometer, and three Waters ultrahydrogel columns (500, 250 and 120 Å pore size and 10, 6 and 6 μm bead size respectively), which were preceded by an ultrahydrogel guard column. An aqueous solution of 0.1 mol/dm³ NaNO₃ was used as an eluent at a flow rate of 0.5 ml/min. Before injection into the GPC system, the polymer solution was filtered through a prefilter-filter combination system compatible

with aqueous solutions. Poly(ethylene glycol) and poly(ethylene oxide) obtained from Waters were used as calibration standards. Previous work from our laboratory reported that GPC determined molecular weights suffered from inconsistency^{2,3}. However, in the present case no inconsistency was detected. Presumably, the samples in the previous work being prepared at 130 °C underwent some hydrolysis which gave rise to inconsistent GPC results.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra of the samples dissolved in D₂O were recorded on a 300 Mz Bruker spectrometer.

Conclusion :

ATRP of acrylamide was attempted in DMF-water medium of various compositions. The use of an extraneous water soluble halide salt LiCl was necessary in order to obtain a good yield of polymer with low PDI and also to keep the polymer in solution at low temperature. No significant effect of CuCl and LiCl was observed on PDI. Lowering the temperature of the reaction to 0 °C yielded better yields. Reduction of the concentration of initiator and the catalyst improved the PDI markedly. Polymers with PDI ≈ 1.12 could be prepared under appropriate conditions. The first order monomer disappearance plots were nonlinear. Also chain extension experiments were not successful. These results indicate that the polymers were nonliving. The molecular weights increased with conversion. Proton NMR analysis indicated the absence of Cl end group in the polymer.

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